

THE APPLICATION OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY TRAINING

G.R.Razzakova

Tashkent University of Information technologies named after
Muhammad al – Khwarizmi/Foreign languages department,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Email: Gulyarazzakova@mail.ru

Abstract— Complete reform of higher education, brought about by the state political and socio-economic transformations, continuous growth the volume of information, an increase in the number of mastered disciplines with stable terms training in universities, put before the system of professional training of specialists a number of serious questions. Also, in the process of training a future specialist, it is important to help him to build his own individual strategy of education, taking into account the motivational the value sphere of the individual and his abilities. The introduction of ITO into the educational process can become the core for the development of a fundamentally new form of lifelong education. The article is devoted to the information technology training and its use in education process.

Key words — digital technology, education process, information technology, computer technology and communication facilities

I.INTRODUCTION

In pedagogy, there is the concept of information technology of education. It the concept characterizes the process of preparing and transmitting information to the student.

Software and computer hardware act as a means of implementing this process.

In information technology training of employees for the transmission of educational information is divided into two components: technical means: computer technology and communication facilities; software can be of various purposes.

To develop lessons using a computer, the teacher must know functional potential and conditions of use of each of these components. How technical and software tools have their own specifics and certain influence the educational process in a way. The pedagogical goals of the application of information technology are: in the development of personality, that is, in the development of thinking, aesthetic education, development of skills in experimental research activities, formation of information culture;

In the fulfillment of a social order: the implementation of a general information user training

(i.e. "computer literacy"), specialist training in any sphere;

In the intensification of the educational process, which suggests improving the quality and efficiency of training, providing motives for cognitive activities, deepening interdisciplinary connections through the integration of subject and information training.

Worldwide research has shown that ICT can lead to improved student learning and better teaching methods. A report made by the National Institute of Multimedia Education in Japan, proved that an increase in student exposure to educational ICT through curriculum integration has a significant and positive impact on student achievement, especially in terms of "Knowledge Comprehension" "Practical skill" and "Presentation skill" in subject areas such as mathematics, science, and social study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodological capabilities of information technologies are considered: visualization of knowledge; Individualization, differentiation of training; The ability to trace the development process of the object, the sequence performing operations (computer demonstrations);

Modeling of objects, processes and phenomena; Development and application of information databases; Access to a significant amount of information presented in an interesting form, thanks to the use of multimedia tools;

Development of skills to process information when working with computer reference books and catalogs; The possibility of self-control; The possibility of training and self-training; Strengthening of motivation for learning (through games, multimedia); The formation of the ability to make the best decision in a complex situations; Development of a certain type of thinking (for example, visual-logical, visual-figurative); The formation of a culture of educational activity;

The formation of information culture; Saving study time.

Information technology training involves the use along with computer technology specialized software. Software an educational tool is a software tool that recreates a separate subject area, where the technology of its study is implemented, are created situations for the implementation of diverse types of educational activities. Such software tools that functionally support various types of educational process, acquired the name of pedagogical software. At this time, there are a large number of various classifications and typologies of pedagogical software.

The use of educational and research projects ensures a higher quality of students' knowledge due to clear planning of work, increased motivation in studying the content of the subject, because the acquired skills are immediately applied in a specific job, initially independently chosen by the child. Students form the ability to work with information to create a project, master software at a higher level, learn to research, put forward their ideas, analyze information, make generalizations, conclusions, and master various forms of reporting on the work done.

5. Multimedia technology

Multimedia - the technology is a mini-technology for the use of modern means of organizing the educational activities of schoolchildren and is focused on the formation of subject competencies in schoolchildren, a search style of thinking, as well as visual-figurative thinking skills.

The use of multimedia allows students to learn how to transfer research skills to the implementation of creative projects. Students apply the knowledge gained in practice; develop such necessary qualities in life as initiative, independence, and self-discipline.

Multimedia technology allows students to develop the skill of self-presentation and public speaking: speech skills and ways to relieve emotional stress before a performance.

Personal computers are computing systems with resources entirely aimed at supporting the activities of one managerial employee. This is the most numerous class of computer technology, which includes personal computers IBM PC and compatible computers, as well as personal computers Macintosh. The intensive development of modern information technologies is due precisely to the widespread use since the early 1980s. Personal computers that combine such qualities as relative cheapness and functionality that is wide enough for a non-professional user.

An automated training system based on hypertext technology allows you to increase the digestibility not only due to the clarity of the information presented. Using dynamic, i.e. changing, hypertext makes it possible to diagnose the student, and then automatically select one of the optimal levels of study of the same topic. Hypertext learning systems provide information in such a way that the student himself, following graphic or text links, can apply various schemes for working with the material. All this makes it possible to implement a differentiated approach to learning.

III. CONCLUSION

In conclusion it can be said that one of the most effective ways to improve the process learning foreign language is the use of computer and Internet technologies in the education system. The computer information model of the education is a kind of transitional phase from a system of traditional teaching methods foreign language.

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